

DISADAPTATION AND ITS MANIFESTATION IN ADOLESCENT BEHAVIOR

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Abstract. This article describes the factors and types of social psychological maladjustment in the character of teenagers, and the scientific and theoretical basis of the manifestation of maladjustment in the behavior of a teenager by psychologists.

Key words: Socialization, adolescent, maladaptation, society, adaptation, personality, attitude, character, study, teacher, morality.

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны факторы и виды социально-психологической дезадаптации характера подростков, а также научно-теоретические основы проявления дезадаптации в поведении подростка психологами.

Ключевые слова: Социализация, подросток, дезадаптация, общество, адаптация, личность, отношение, характер, учеба, педагог, мораль.

In the process of socialization, a person acquires confidence and socially acceptable forms of morality necessary for a normal life in society. Despite pedagogical neglect, lagging in studies, skipping classes, conflicts with teachers and classmates, the subjects do not experience a sharp deformation of value-normative perceptions. In this case, the value of work for a person remains high enough, it is directed towards choosing a profession and acquiring it, the opinions of others will not be different for him, and social and referent relations will retain their importance.

Socialization means the experience of social life, social relations and social values (speech and knowledge, human thinking and consciousness, to the surrounding world and self-attitudes, skills and knowledge, norms, habits, qualities, needs, abilities, etc.) should be understood as a whole multifaceted process. However, the assimilation of the achievements of human civilization does not proceed in the same way as success in different individuals.

Factors of formation of social psychological maladjustment in the character of teenagers. The concept of adaptation occupies a large place in modern psychology. In addition, there are different points of view on this problem. In the pedagogical encyclopedia, the concept of adaptation is defined as follows: "Adaptation" (Greek adapta-tio-adaptation), adaptation of the organism to external conditions. The basis of adaptation is the reaction of the organism that allows maintaining its internal stability in the external environment. "Adaptation" ensures that the organism maintains its normal development and optimization abilities in various conditions. In the theoretical analysis of the concept of adaptation in "pedagogy and psychology", the concept of personal development is considered as a process of transition to a relatively stable stage of personal development. (E.V.Ilenkov, A.V.Petrovsky, D.I.Feldstein)

Personality development is seen by these researchers as penetration and integration into a new social environment. A.V.Petrovsky considers the first stage of personality

formation to be the stage of adaptation. At this stage, it is understood that a person acquires social norms and criteria established in society, as well as certain methods and means of activity. When entering a new social environment, the subject must first master the established norms, and only then can he express himself as a person. If the individual is not able to overcome the difficulties in the process of adaptation, it can cause complicated disorders in the development of the individual, that is, adaptation is individualization in the process of socialization. When a child comes into the world, he enters into a unique relationship with the environment that surrounds him. The environment is not only a factor determining the child's way of life, but also the main source that promotes or inhibits the development of his mental processes. L.S.Vygotsky, in his thoughts on child development, stated that "the result of education is given in his head." According to G. B.Shoumarov, the fact that adolescence is a difficult and complicated period is connected with many psychological, physiological and social factors. During this period, the essence of all aspects of development: physical, mental, moral, social, etc. changes. During this period, serious changes occur in a teenager's life, psyche, physiological processes, and social status.

E.A.Orlova divides adaptive processes into three main fundamental types:

1. The first type. Active attempts to change the established social situation.
2. The second type "Alienation syndrome" is an attempt to avoid solving the existing problem.
3. The third type is "dialogue" to come to an agreement with the changed social environment.

P.S.Kuznetsov in his research gave a psychological description of 3 stages of adaptation (high, medium, low): Those with a high level of adaptation are characterized by activity, confidence in their own strength and capabilities. , they are in a relationship with a sincere interest in the events and happenings around them. Their position can be considered stable. Impulsivity, experiencing good and bad times in life, and emotional instability are typical in the middle adaptation stage. The instability of the situation of those at this stage is explained by the fact that they either strive for a higher stage of social adaptation, or fall into a lower stage of adaptation. A low level of vital activity is observed in cases of lower adaptation. People at this stage are characterized by self-doubt, dependence on the opinions of others, submissiveness, and often a persistent depression. M.I.Enikeev describes the process of social adaptation as the acquisition of social norms and criteria by the adolescent and active adaptation of the individual to new conditions in the social environment.

A. A.Rean emphasized that the direction of adaptive processes has an "external" and "internal" direction. "External" orientation of the adaptive process is understood as adaptation by the individual to the social situation surrounding him, active assimilation, and adaptation to his own needs and direction. The state of the adaptive process in the "internal" direction is characterized by the correction of the social institutions of the individual on the basis of socially established stereotypes. This type of adaptation focuses on changing the person himself. Both types of social adaptation are an active process as a stage of personality development. The author also emphasizes the existence of a third type of adaptation that combines both types of adaptation. That is, in the case of an imbalance of some kind of adaptive process, the person tries to find other adaptive resources in the social space. According to the author, the tendency of a person in a "conform" social environment to develop himself, to change himself, to correct himself in the assimilation of established social

institutions, standards and criteria means a state of maladaptation, not adaptation. Disadaptation is the subject's inability to adapt to social standards and criteria. In psychological literature, the following types of social psychological disadaptation are classified. Psychogenic disadaptation is caused by disturbances in the process of communication with important people in the surrounding social environment of a teenager. In many cases, this may be the result of a breakdown in relationships with peers.

Communication with emotionally close people serves as the main source of the formation of emotional experiences of a teenager. In this process, negative experiences of a teenager with some close people in the close social environment are compensated in communication with other close people. From this point of view, if it is compensated through communication with teachers, parents, and family members, not all conflict situations with peers may cause a pathogenic dezadaptatsya in a teenager. The probability of maladaptation in adolescents increases when the compensation process in communication is carried out through an antisocial social environment. But, on the other hand, the positive communication of a teenager with his peers makes it possible to compensate for the disturbances in interpersonal relationships in the family or at school with the teacher.

Aggravation of the adolescent's family anamnesis in the cause of maladjustment: dysfunctional families and upbringing outside the family, father who drinks a lot, mental illness of one of the parents, disharmonious relationships and disagreements in the family, wrong parenting to the teenager in childhood. they differ in their attitude, borderline or high level of psychopathology.

The following are indicated as a factor in the formation of maladjustment in adolescents:

1. Lack of warm emotional relationships in the family (you have everything. What else do you need?).
2. Pampering teenagers too much, fulfilling their wishes quickly. Insignificant restrictions can lead to the emergence of suicidal tendencies in teenagers (the clothes they like, their parents don't like them, they don't buy the promised phone from an expensive brand, etc.).
3. Chronic conflicts between parents in the family, father's alcohol consumption, second marriage, absence of a son in the household. A teenager's inability to correct these situations.
4. Efforts by parents to constantly control the behavior of teenagers.
5. The fact that his relationship with his loved one, which is important for a teenager, was not strictly accepted by his parents (you embarrassed the neighborhood, it's better not to have a child like you, if I hear anything about that again, I will kill you)
6. Indifference of family members to the successes or problems of the teenager.

The state of maladjustment is healthy, or there are various neuropsychological disorders (oligophrenic adolescents with physical defects, organic disorders do not belong to this category), it is possible to include the formation in adolescents. According to psychologists, socio-psychological factors that cause maladaptation are conditionally divided into 2 groups In the process of social or objective-personal or subjective disadaptation, both factors appear interrelated. Disadaptation in the field of education is manifested in disorders in educational activities, behavioral deviations, conflicts in interpersonal relationships with adults and peers, increased anxiety, and disorders in personality development.

Psychomotor retardation is one of the manifestations of neurodynamic disorders manifested in the state of disadaptation. Such teenagers are characterized by slow development of mental activity, reduced motor activity, low expression of emotional reactions. Due to their inability to react quickly in various situations, these teenagers experience serious difficulties in the process of interpersonal relations with their peers and in their educational activities. Neurodynamic disorders are also manifested in irregularities in the course of mental processes. There are cases of emotional instability in behavioral manifestations, easy transition from extreme activity to extreme passivity, and vice versa, from passivity in general movement to uncontrollable hyperactivity. Complaints about getting tired and feeling bad during classes are often returned, and in these cases, despite the rapid changes in the level of mastering, the level of intellectual development is relatively advanced, the level of mastering is observed. Developmental features of this category of teenagers often cause secondary difficulties, caused by teachers' inability to correctly understand their age and individual typological characteristics.

Loss of activity in situations of stress and frustration is another characteristic of maladaptation in adolescents. In this situation, the communication system of adolescents is not complete, first of all, the breakdown of relations with peers and people in the close social environment leads to the appearance of such experiences as "loneliness", "alienation", "boredom". It is during the period of adolescence that the cases of social and psychological maladjustment, if not detected and eliminated in time, can have consequences that can have a serious negative impact on the maturity of the adolescent personality. That is, this situation causes a further decrease in the adolescent's self-esteem, conflicts in interpersonal relationships of various natures, a decrease in motivation in relation to educational activities that are of special importance in the development of a person, the emergence of a state of neurosis and even mental disorders. it can. Because of this, many psychologists paid special attention to studying this problem.

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